

Radiation-Driven Instability in Layered Protoplanetary Disk Structures

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Abstract Standard astrochemical models suggest that protoplanetary disks are primarily composed of molecular hydrogen and helium, with minor molecular species detectable at infrared and millimeter wavelengths. Traditionally, the thermal scale height of a rotating protoplanetary disk is derived from the isothermal sound speed of molecular hydrogen, $C_s = \sqrt{k_B T / \mu m_H}$. Growing observational evidence (e.g., from ALMA and JWST) now suggests that radiative pressure from the stellar environment may significantly alter the disk's vertical morphology. However, this classical treatment neglects the role of radiative pressure and assumes a purely hydrogen-dominated composition. Numerical experiments, such as radiation-hydrodynamic simulations, suggests that when star light penetrates the inner parts of the disk due to irradiance instability, photon momentum transfer (PMT) becomes dominant, thus leading to radiation-hydrodynamic coupling. Here, we extend the irradiance-driven instability and we yield a mass-dependent, layered disk structure of scale height H_{rad} . The layered disk structure elevates the optical line by an inclined inflection $\Delta H \propto H_{\text{rad}}$. More photons penetrate through the perturbed disk annulus, leading to an increase in the local sound speed and a more pronounced thermal pressure scale height H_{therm} . We report that, for a rotating Keplerian disk, the vertical settling of the gaseous species at H_{tracer} , is strongly dependent on the balance between gravity and radiative heating. Our numerical study of the protoplanetary disks PDS 70, HD 100546 and HD 163296 revealed that H_{tracer} self-consistently maps the CO tracer in the intermediate disk layers, where it remains shielded from UV photodissociation at aspect ratios of $0.494 < H/R < 0.550$. This method holds promise for future gas-tracer mapping in protoplanetary disks.

Key words: radiative transfer — Physical Data and Processes protoplanetary disks — Planetary Systems radiation mechanisms: non-thermal — Physical Data and Processes radiation mechanisms: thermal — Physical Data and Processes

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context

Recent advancements by the Atacama Large Millimeter / submillimeter Array (ALMA) and the Disk Substructures at High Angular Resolution Project (DSHARP) have significantly improved our ability to probe young stellar systems such as the T Tauri and Herbig Ae/Be stars (*see.*, Stapper, L. M. et al. 2022; Brittain et al. 2023; Wichittanakom et al. 2020). ALMA’s unprecedented resolution and sensitivity at millimeter and submillimeter wavelengths enable detailed observations of the physical and chemical properties of protoplanetary disks (Rich et al. 2022). These observations have given us crucial insights into the processes of star and planet formation. ALMA employs high-resolution receivers to detect molecular line emissions across different vertical layers of the protoplanetary disk (Rosenfeld et al. 2013; Villenave, M. et al. 2020). Spectral line observations at varying excitation states reveal distinct thermal and density gradients, differentiating the UV-irradiated upper disk layers from the thermally isolated mid-plane region (Lin et al. 2023; Villenave, M. et al. 2020). This capability has reshaped our understanding of planet birthplaces by revealing how key processes such as chemical reactions and dust behavior vary with height. As a result, these mechanisms regulate the inventory of atmospheric volatiles in nascent planets (Molyarova et al. 2017; Desch et al. 2017).

These disks are typically characterized by a flared geometry, where the disk surface height increases with radial distance. This flaring occurs because the disk surface temperature decreases with the semi-major axis, leading to an increase in the local scale height (Rafikov & Colle 2006; Men’shchikov & Henning 1997). This flared structure results in a disk surface that is not flat but inclined outwards as we move away from the center of the *YSO* (*see.*, Figure 1 (left panel)). The thermal balance of an accretion disk is maintained by two primary heating mechanisms, *i.e.*: 1) the internal viscous dissipation and; 2) irradiance from the *YSO*. A more accurate profile of viscous dissipation is given by the α -disk model. The theory was first proposed in 1973 by Nikolai Ivanovich Shakura (1945 - 2021) and Rashid Alievich Sunyaev (1943 - 2024) and it suggests that, viscous heating occurs as a result of turbulent stresses which transport angular momentum outwards (*see.*, Shakura & Sunyaev 1973). For a rotating Keplerian disk, the effective viscosity of the disk is given by $\nu = \alpha C_s H_{\text{therm}}$, where ν is the turbulent viscosity, α is a dimensionless parameter which quantifies the strength of the turbulence and H_{therm} is the disk’s thermal scale height (*i.e.*, $H_{\text{therm}} = C_s/\Omega$).

Viscous heating arises primarily from the dissipation of energy due to frictional forces between differentially rotating gas layers. As the material moves through the disk, the shear force between layers generates turbulent motions, which converts kinetic energy into heat. This heat is responsible for increasing the local temperatures of the disk, especially in regions where the gas undergoes rapid rotation, such as in the inner parts of the protoplanetary disk (Alarcón et al. 2023a; Chambers 2009; Alarcón et al. 2023b). This conversion of gravitational potential energy into thermal energy is fundamental to the disk’s temperature and pressure support. Such a disk is referred to as an active disk. The vertical structure of the disk is determined by the balance between the gravitational force pulling the material downwards

towards the mid-plane and the upward thermal pressure support $P_{\text{therm}} = \rho C_s^2$, in a hydrogen-rich gas column of density ρ .

In general, circumstellar gaseous disks are expected to be gas pressure-dominated. This condition is used to assume hydrostatic equilibrium (*i.e.*, $dp/dz = -\rho g_z$) between gravity and the thermal pressure, while maintaining a scale height H_{therm} , above the disk mid-plane. The study of protoplanetary accretion disks also started with particular attention to the irradiation effect of the central *YSO*. In some cases irradiation heating dominates over viscous heating. Such an irradiated disk is often called a passive disk, in contrast to an active disk, where viscous heating is internal.

Optical light from the star is absorbed high up in the disk by small dust grains (Wu & Lithwick 2021), and the radiation from these grains illuminates the molecular layer, thus raising the disk's temperature (*see.*, Figure 1, panel 2). This heating disrupts the disk's thermal equilibrium by raising the local sound speed and inflating the disk in regions where radiative heating exceeds cooling (Vick & Lithwick 2022; Kutra et al. 2024). This instability then creates dense, cold mid-plane layers and tenuous, hot surface layers thus altering the pressure gradient (Kutra et al. 2024). In some regimes, it allows starlight to penetrate deeper into the disk, enabling photochemistry (e.g., CO dissociation) at unusual depths.

Active disk models have been successful in explaining the effects of thermal pressure in the vertical geometry in hydrogen gas dominated protoplanetary disks (*see.*, Shakura & Sunyaev 1973; Chiang & Goldreich 1997; Dullemond & Dominik 2004; D'Alessio et al. 2006). However, the role of radiative pressure in the vertical stratification of the disk cannot be ignored (Montesinos et al. 2021; Haworth et al. 2016a,b; Boehler et al. 2013). The works by in Montesinos et al. 2021, though receiving little attention, raises an interesting possibility.

Their study focused on how radiative pressure impacts the vertical geometry of the disk, in regions where temperatures can reach $1000K$. Their numerical experiments revealed that, radiative pressure effects create a vertical, optically thick column of gas and dust at the protoplanet location, casting a shadow in scattered light. While Montesinos et al. 2021 focused on the effects of radiative columns and shadows in the evolution of the disk, their results alluded to potential downstream thermal effects where this shadow may induce local cooling and alter the disk's scale height beyond the shadowed region.

However, in the modest view, the anisotropic nature of radiative pressure and its collective role in the vertical stratification of gas and dust above the disk's mid-plane are not examined in the current analytical studies. Thus, such analytical studies are few, and often the boundary conditions are not appropriate to maintain the vertical geometry of the disk (*see.*, Haworth et al. 2016b; Vinković 2009; Montesinos et al. 2021). The analytical framework for irradiation instability has traditionally emphasized the role of thermal waves generated by starlight absorption in flaring disk geometries (Kutra et al. 2024; Vick & Lithwick 2022). In this context, the contribution of radiation pressure is typically addressed in relation to dust dynamics (Vinković & Čemeljić 2021, 2024), particularly in the inner disk regions where dust erosion and lofting are dominant. However, the competitive strength of radiative pressure beyond its effects on dust has received little attention, thus leaving the coupling between radiation-driven forces and vertical gas stratification less well constrained in current disk models.

Moreover, according to the prevailing astrochemical models of Molyarova et al. 2017 and Desch et al. 2017, the protoplanetary disk is composed of approximately 70–80% of hydrogen by mass, 20–28% of helium (Molyarova et al. 2017), with the remaining fraction consisting of minor molecular species detectable at infrared (Chiu et al. 2007) and millimeter wavelength¹. Although these gases have long been detected using modern interferometry, the classical thermal scale height model has been more commonly used to model the vertical distribution of the disk gases, in systems where the sound speed C_s only reflects the thermal properties of a hydrogen gas-dominated protoplanetary disk (Wu & Lithwick 2021; Men’shchikov & Henning 1997; Haworth et al. 2016a; Vinković 2009). As a result, distinguishing between the effects of radiative and thermal pressure on different gaseous species remains challenging, partly due to the limited thermochemical constraints in current models (Gräfe et al. 2013; Öberg et al. 2021). This limitation suggests that the standard thermal scale-height framework is insufficient for accurately resolving the disk’s vertical structure. In this paper, we suggest that — radiative pressure is the key missing link in our current understanding of passive disks — not merely as a uniform force but as a selective mechanism that acts differentially on species with distinct radiation absorption cross-sections and molecular masses.

1.2 Methods

Realizing this gap to be filled in our current understanding of radiation-hydrodynamic coupling in protoplanetary disk’s, the key question we seek to address here is to do with the vertical mass distribution of gases in a system where radiative heating becomes dominant. Despite the differences from model to model, most have in common to simulate the radial evolution of the gas, yet the challenge often lies in representing the magnitude of the inclined inflection due to the irradiance instability and its interaction with the thermal pressure support. To address this, first we seek for a better understanding of the conditions that trigger the irradiance instability in protoplanetary disks. To gain this better understanding, we analyze Wu & Lithwick 2021’s hydrodynamical model of the geometry of a perturbed passive disk in Section 2.

There, we reveal that, the peculiar geometric features of the inclined inflection gradient $m_{\text{rad}} = \Delta H_{\text{rad}}/\Delta R$, are strongly dependent on the wavelength of the incident photon and the particle’s mass. In Section 3, we present a simple radiation-hydrodynamic coupling model based on the principles of linear momentum, neither of which is new to this work. We do so both to connect to the previous misunderstanding that passive disks are stable and to highlight the differences between such a treatment (Duchêne et al. 2017; Watanabe & Lin 2008). By that, we derive the radiative transfer velocity, V_{rad} . We found that, in a radiative pressure dominated regime, the radiative transfer velocity is mass dependent. This results in

¹ ALMA returned high-resolution images of the protoplanetary disk around IRAS 04302+2247, which were taken edge-on at sub-millimeter wavelengths (0.9–1.3 mm). These high resolution images revealed a more pronounced vertical differentiation of CO , CS , and H_2CO molecules, while tracing different layers of the disk structure (Lin et al. 2023). CO ($J = 2-1$) emission dominates the upper, warmer layers (see Figure B.1 in Appendix B) due to its susceptibility to UV photo-dissociation near the surface, while CS ($J = 5-4$) is detectable at intermediate heights, where sulfur-bearing chemistry is enhanced by shock-driven processes or localized UV penetration (Podio, L. et al. 2020). In contrast, H_2CO (formaldehyde) emission is more concentrated near the disk’s mid-plane, likely due to its formation on icy dust grains and subsequent thermal or non-thermal desorption in the colder, denser regions.

a selective process, where particles of the same kind are vertically displaced above the disk mid-plane, forming a layer of thickness ΔH_{rad} .

This leads to a very interesting result. We found that the post-collisional motion of the particle is directed at an angle ϕ , relative to the incident photon’s original plane of motion. In the limiting case where $\phi = 90^\circ$, the kinetic energy transferred to the particle reaches its maximum. This corresponds to an orthogonal transverse deflection from the photon’s original trajectory, which is sufficient to counteract the gravitational potential of the disk’s mid-plane. This layered configuration gives rise to a perturbed disk geometry in which the inclined inflection, ΔH , is equivalent to the radiative scale height, H_{rad} . This marks the height of a radiatively driven displacement, which we shall discuss extensively in Section 5.

In Section 4 however, we go on one step further to ascertain whether the photon-coupled particle remain gravitationally stable or unstable at this altitude under radiative imbalance. We first address whether the free-fall of the particle is a first-order approximation of the Jeans 1929 collapse criterion. This involves simplifying the full gravitational instability analysis by assuming an isothermal, homogeneous medium with small perturbations. We then utilized the self-similar solutions of Larson 1969 and Penston 1969 to examine how the vertical forces affect the orbital stability of the disk under mutual perturbations. This leads us to an important result. We yield the mid-plane analogue of the free-fall velocity V_{ff} under the Jeans 1929 collapse criterion, but in a pressureless system. We note that this approximation is valid in the vicinity of the disk’s atmosphere, where thermal support is minimal, but gravitational collapse is inevitable (i.e., $C_s^2 \ll V_{\text{ff}}^2$).

In Section 5, we introduce a simplifying assumption that — at the nascent stages of the disk’s evolution, particles occupy orbits extending beyond the thermal scale height, where they remain gravitationally bound by the vertical component of V_{ff} and the outward centrifugal force. We found that, at this scale height, the particle attains a quasi-stable angular momentum, and its downward gravitational acceleration is counter balanced by V_{rad} and the local sound speed (i.e., $\Omega_K^2 H_{\text{tracer}} = V_{\text{ff}}^2 - (C_s^2 + V_{\text{rad}}^2)$).

In Section 6, we performed a numerical investigation to establish whether H_{tracer} could potentially serve as a viable proxy for the vertical distribution of CO isotopologues and other primordial gaseous species above the mid-plane of the disk. Rather than treating CO emission as a surface or mid-plane phenomenon, the study considered how emission arises from layers where gravity, temperature, and mass converge to enhance radiative output. Using representative models of the PDS 70, HD 100546, and HD 163296 disks, the simulation probed the effective height at which tracer molecules contribute significantly to disk emission. We found out that, CO is neither confined to the mid-plane nor limited to the irradiated surface, but is instead concentrated in thermally elevated strata—intermediate layers characterized by an aspect ratio in the range $0.494 < H/R < 0.550$, where vertical gradients in temperature and density remain favorable for molecular excitation and radiative escape. The analysis of Law et al. (2022), Law et al. 2021 and Law et al. 2024 strongly suggests that CO and its isotopologues trace the intermediate vertical layers, well within the range ($H/R \approx 0.5$) we infer for HD 100546, HD 163296 and PDS 70 respectively.

2 THE PASSIVE DISK

2.1 A Passive Disk at Equilibrium

Here, we follow the concepts and notations in Chiang & Goldreich 1997 to study the source of photon emission in passive disks. Figure 1 (left panel) shows a schematic of a passive disk at equilibrium. The background shading represents the density of matter, relative to their mid-plane density. Depending on the dominance of the gaseous species, the star's optical light is absorbed by the gas and dust grains near the species specific optical surface (SSOS), which lies a few scale heights (H_{rad}) above the mid-plane. The radiative scale height H_{rad} , shall be discussed extensively in Section 6. This layer re-radiates half of the luminosity (Wu & Lithwick 2021) it receives down into the disk, and the latter then re-emits this energy at longer wavelengths in the scattered layer. The amount of heating a disk receives is determined by the flaring of its optical surface ΔH . In Figure 1, the relevant star rays received by a radial zone of concern are those bound by the two arrows. When balancing the heating against blackbody cooling and insisting on vertical hydrostatic equilibrium, a flared solution is found for these disks (Kusaka et al. 1970; Chiang & Goldreich 1997).

Figure 1: A schematic depiction of a passive protoplanetary disk at equilibrium (left) and under perturbation (right), for a radial range of $0 < R < 18\text{AU}$. The gas density is represented by color shading, where $SSOS_0$ denotes the vertical gas scale height, and $SSOS_3$ marks the optical surface where incoming starlight (green line) is absorbed. The angle of the white segment indicates the fraction of intercepted starlight. When the mid-plane temperature increases (right), the intercepted starlight also increases due to: (1) the optical surface rising in proportion to the radiative scale height $\Delta H \propto H_{\text{rad}}$ and (2) an increase in the starlight's penetration depth. Schematic based on: Wu & Lithwick 2021.

2.1.1 The Perturbed Passive Disk

Figure 1 (panel 2) illustrates what happens to the disk when a localized thermal perturbation increases the scale height. There are two effects. First, the optical surface rises in proportion to the radiative scale height $\Delta H \propto H_{\text{rad}}$ (dashed curve). This is what is considered in D'Alessio et al. 2006 and Wu & Lithwick 2021. The disk intercepts a bit more stellar flux, but not

enough to overcome the extra blackbody cooling from a now hotter disk. As a result, the perturbation damps away. But there is another effect. Consider first the inner half of the scale height perturbation. The slope of the optical surface is increased (*i.e.*, $m_{\text{rad}} = \Delta H_{\text{rad}}/\Delta R$) there, so the star's rays shine more directly overhead (*i.e.*, closer to the surface normal) and can penetrate more deeply into the disk. This effect is analogous to stellar limb darkening, but now for absorption (Neilson, H. R. & Lester, J. B. 2011).

Conversely, at the outer part of the perturbation, starlight penetrates more shallowly owing to the more tangent slant. As a result, the opening angle between the two rays is increased. This means excess heating, and given the right perturbation, it can overcome the excess cooling and drive an instability. Interestingly, an extreme manifestation of stronger flaring leading to enhanced heating occurs in the inner rim of the protoplanetary disk (Dullemond & Dominik 2005). In this region, the star's rays enter the disk almost head-on. The strong heating puffs up the inner rim into a wall. The disk itself traps and re-radiates photons due to multiple scatterings within its layers. This process modifies the radiation field and contributes significantly to the vertical transport of material in the disk. The main purpose of this study is to demonstrate how the irradiation instability alters observable PMT signatures through coupled radiation-hydrodynamic effects. We investigate how this thermal-radiative mechanism gives rise to an observable gas-phase morphology in the protoplanetary disk, wherein gas and small dust particles are arranged into chemically distinct layers detectable through multi-wavelength disk tomography.

2.2 Assumptions in Our Radiative Disk Scale Height (RDSH) Model

To study the vertical stability of passive protoplanetary disks, we make a number of simplifying assumptions to highlight what we believe are the most relevant factors to consider in the short treatment of radiation-hydrodynamic coupling. These are:

1. The disk is in a steady-state or quasi-steady evolution;
2. The sound speed and the radiative transfer velocity are both treated as restorative forces;
3. The gas and dust components are partially coupled;
4. The formation of the *YSO* and the rotating flat disk is reasonably well understood.

In-addition to this, we also introduce a string of other simplifications, which we will describe as we go along. In Section 6, we assess how some of these assumptions and how varying them may qualitatively affect our results.

3 PHOTON MOMENTUM TRANSFER IN THE PASSIVE PROTOPLANETARY DISK'S

3.1 The Radiative Transfer Velocity Equation

Here, we hypothesis that, in a passive protoplanetary disk, photon momentum transfer processes begins when an incident photon from a *YSO* collides with the particle, during which the photon transfers most of its energy and momentum to the particle, thus leading to an inclined trajectory relative to the photon's original plane (radial plane) of motion. The resulting motion of the particle is characterized by a radiative transfer velocity, V_{rad} . Before

Table 1: Radiative velocities for different gaseous species across the electromagnetic radiation bands.

Radiation Band	Wavelength (m)	Radiation Source (Protostar)	V_{rad} Hydrogen (m/s)	V_{rad} Electrons (m/s)	V_{rad} Helium (m/s)	V_{rad} CO (m/s)	References
X-rays	1.00e-11	Class 0, I, II	3.97e+4	7.28e+7	1.00e+4	1.43e+3	[1]
EUV	1.00e-8	Class II, III	3.97e+1	7.28e+4	1.00e+1	1.43e+0	[2]
FUV	1.22e-7	Class II	3.25e+0	6.00e+3	8.18e-1	1.17e-1	[3]
NUV	2.00e-7	Class II, III	2.00e+0	3.64e+3	5.00e-1	7.13e-2	[4]
Optical	4.00e-7	Class II, III	1.00e+0	1.82e+3	2.50e-1	3.56e-2	[5]
NIR	7.00e-7	Class I, II, III	5.67e-1	1.04e+3	1.42e-1	2.04e-2	[6]
MIR	5.00e-6	Class 0, I	7.94e-2	1.46e+2	2.00e-2	2.85e-3	[7]
FIR	2.50e-5	Class 0, I	1.56e-2	2.91e+1	4.00e-3	5.70e-4	[8]

References: [1] Laos et al. 2021, [2] Stacy et al. 2013 and Laos et al. 2021, [3] Stacy et al. 2013, [4] Stacy et al. 2013, [5] Stacy et al. 2013, [6] Harsono et al. 2023, [7] Laos et al. 2021 and [8] Stacy et al. 2013.

photon-*to*-particle interactions can take place, the photon must possess enough momentum to overcome the particle's own inertia *i.e.*, $P_{\text{photon}} = \frac{h\nu_i}{c}$; where h is Planck's constant, ν_i is the incident photon's frequency, and c is the speed of light. The stationary particle has a zero initial momentum (*i.e.*, $P_{\text{particle}} = 0$), thus we yield a *total* initial momentum of $P_{\text{initial}} = \frac{h\nu_i}{c}$.

After collision, the photon transfers part of its momentum and kinetic energy to the particle thus reducing its own momentum to $P'_{\text{photon}} = \frac{h\nu_f}{c}$; where ν_f is the photon's new frequency (*i.e.*, $\nu_f < \nu_i$). Concurrently, the particle gains momentum $P'_{\text{particle}} = mV_{\text{rad}}$. According to the law of conservation of linear momentum, the total initial momentum is equal to the total final momentum, thus we have:

$$\frac{h\nu_{\text{ff}}}{c} + mV_{\text{rad}} = \frac{h\nu_i}{c}. \quad (1)$$

Solving for V_{rad} yields:

$$V_{\text{rad}} = \frac{h}{m} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_i} - \frac{1}{\lambda_f} \right). \quad (2)$$

If the photon is completely absorbed (*i.e.*, $\lambda_f \rightarrow \infty$), then the imparted velocity simplifies to:

$$V_{\text{rad}} = \frac{h}{m\lambda}. \quad (3)$$

What this means is that, the photon will travel at a post collisional velocity $V_{\text{rad}} = h/m\lambda$, with a kinetic energy $KE = 1/2mV_{\text{rad}}^2$, which is strongly dependent on the mass of the gaseous species and the wavelength of the incident photon. For example, X-Ray emission from the *YSO* is capable of accelerating a gaseous hydrogen particle to velocities up to $V_{\text{rad}} = 3.97 \times 10^4 \text{ m/s}$ after collision (*see.*, Table 1), while NUV photons from accretion driven emission (Yang et al. 2011) are capable of accelerating the hydrogen particle to velocities up to $V_{\text{rad}} = 2 \text{ m/s}$.

Regardless, these velocities are insufficient to overcome the escape velocities in most *YSO*'s, (*e.g.*, Haro 6-5B, HL Tau, CL Tau, and TW Hydrae), so these energetic particles

Figure 2: The heat map for $\text{Log}_{10}(V_{\text{rad}})$ for different particle types across electromagnetic radiation bands.

occupy the upper-mid regions of the disk. If we approximate our disk as a blackbody emitter, then our wavelength λ can be expressed in terms of the temperature of the disk by mere application of the Wien's Displacement Law *i.e.*, $\lambda = \frac{b}{T}$, where $b = 2.897 \times 10^{-3} \text{m} \cdot \text{K}$. Substituting $\frac{T}{b} = \frac{1}{\lambda}$ into Eq. (3) simplifies our radiative transfer velocity equation to:

$$V_{\text{rad}} = \frac{hT}{bm}. \quad (4)$$

Assuming that, prior to collisional scattering, the photon is moving away from a source (*e.g.*, YSO), in the radial direction parallel to the disk's mid-plane. If the particle moves at an angle ϕ relative to the photon's original plane of motion, then the vertical component of the radiative transfer velocity is $V_{\text{rad}} \sin \phi$, and the in-plane component is $V_{\text{rad}} \cos \phi$. Eq. (4) can now be expressed in vector form as:

$$\vec{V}_{\text{rad}} = \frac{hT}{bm} \cos \phi \hat{\mathbf{r}} + \frac{hT}{bm} \sin \phi \hat{\mathbf{z}}, \quad (5)$$

:where $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$ is the radial unit vector, typically in the direction of the disk's mid-plane and $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$ is a unit vector perpendicular to the mid-plane of the disk. Due to isotropization of scattered radiation, the trajectory of the scattered photon isn't considered here, as it is not central to our understanding of the effects of PMT in the vertical geometry of the disk. Ignoring the scattered photon trajectories allows the model to focus analytically on the first-order vertical momentum transfer, avoiding complexities associated with scattering phase functions, which would complicate without significantly altering the conclusions about layering. Thus, for the purpose of this study, we set the angle ϕ to 90° to yield the maximum kinetic energy. In

the standard disk model, such a trajectory resemble a mid-plane analogue of the Jeans 1929 collapse criterion, which we explore next.

4 THE FREE-FALL VELOCITY

The interplay between gravity and thermal-radiative pressure is of prime importance in any theory of the disk’s evolution Montesinos et al. 2021; Vick & Lithwick 2022; Haworth et al. 2016a. This equilibrium dictates the distribution of the disk’s radial density and thickness, all of which are crucial in the processes of planet formation and angular momentum transport. Here, we use the concept and notation of the Jeans 1929 instability criterion to identify the initial conditions necessary for the onset of a radiative heating regime. This will be accomplished in Section 4.1 *via* a subtle approach, where the free-fall velocity of a pressureless, spherically symmetric cloud is obtained. In Section 4.2, we adopt the mid-plane analogue of the free-fall velocity by using the similarity solution of Larson 1969 and Penston 1969. This approach assumes ballistic in-fall (negligible magnetic or turbulent support) and provides a first-order approximation of the velocity field during the early stages of disk formation.

4.1 The Spherically Symmetric Collapse Scenario

Here, we consider the conditions of gravitational instability that trigger runaway collapse in spherically symmetric collapse of a giant molecular cloud of gas and dust. We derive the free-fall velocity of a collapsing gas cloud, by considering the motion of a particle P located at the boundary of a giant molecular cloud (GMC). This particle must accelerate at free-fall, as the molecular cloud of gas and dust begins to collapse under its own gravity. We assume that — for a rotating spherical gas cloud like a young nebula just beginning to collapse, the collapse timescale is given by a free-fall time, t_{ff} . Here, we neglect magnetic effects (as will be shown later in this section, these forces do not change the essence of our argument, hence we do not need to worry about them here) and we consider only a simplified scenario where we have a uniform rotating GMC collapsing under its own gravity. Furthermore, we also assume that, the gas and dust are confined within a specific region by the GMC ’s own gravity. Given that the free-fall time at a pressure gradient in the interior of the clump that is negligibly small is given by:

$$t_{\text{ff}}^2 = \frac{3\pi}{32G\rho}, \quad (6)$$

where ρ is the density of the GMC of mass, M_{cloud} and volume V . The free-fall time $t_{\text{ff}}^2 = \pi^2 R^3 / 8GM_{\text{cloud}}$ can be measured by looking at particle P , at the edge of the spherical gas cloud at a radius R . The particle feels an acceleration $g = -GM_{\text{cloud}}/R^2$ from the rest of the molecular cloud by making use of the divergence theorem, whereby the point mass only feels the gravitational force from the mass interior to its radius (Jeans 1929). The rate at which the mass of the gaseous envelop depletes at constant radius is:

$$\eta_t = \frac{\partial M_{\text{cloud}}}{\partial t} = -\frac{\pi^2 R^3}{4Gt_{\text{ff}}^3}. \quad (7)$$

Given the result in (7), we can now define the compaction parameter, η_R , as the rate of change of the gas cloud's mass with respect to its radius, *i.e.*:

$$\eta_R = \frac{\partial M_{\text{cloud}}}{\partial R} = \frac{3\pi^2 R^2}{8Gt_{\text{ff}}^2}. \quad (8)$$

The contraction rate of the *GMC* can be found by considering the ratio between the differentials η_t and η_R , *i.e.*:

$$\frac{\partial R}{\partial t} = \frac{\eta_t}{\eta_R}. \quad (9)$$

Once gravity overcomes the gas cloud's internal pressure, the molecular cloud begins to contract at a velocity:

$$V_{\text{ff}} = \frac{\partial R}{\partial t} = -\frac{2R}{3t_{\text{ff}}}. \quad (10)$$

This means that if gravity overcomes the internal pressure support, the system undergoes run-away collapse thus leading to a steepening velocity field as material falls inwards. With the free-fall velocity of a spherically symmetric gas cloud ascertained, we now turn our attention to the disk's mid-plane variant, where gas densities are highest and vertical support from pressure is weakest, making the region most susceptible to gravitationally driven collapse and the onset of local instabilities (Armitage 2017). An analogous criterion for gravitational collapse in this two-dimensional (or effectively two-dimensional for a thin disk) environment can now be considered.

4.2 The Mid-plane Variant

The formation of the mid-plane and the subsequent collapse of material towards this dense, cold region can be traced back to the evolution of the progenitor molecular cloud (Lee et al. 2023). This process is a precursor to the disk's formation, as the initial collapse under the Jeans 1929 collapse criterion leads to flattening of the disk due to conservation of angular momentum. Although the centrifugal force prevents radial collapse, vertical collapse remains active as gravity continues to pull material towards the disk's mid-plane. This gravitational in-fall can only be counteracted by vertical pressure support (Armitage 2017) and if this upward pressure gradient weakens due to radiative cooling and thermal energy loss, the disk would in-principle experience a secondary gravitational in-fall of material along the z -axis.

In the upper layers, where the pressure gradient is minimal (*see.*, Figure 3), the collapse mirrors a $1D$ free-fall motion towards the mid-plane. This vertical in-fall is analogous to the original Jeans 1929 collapse, with its velocity profile inherited from the collapse of the parent *GMC* (also *see.*, Rafikov & Colle 2006). Such a process is sustained by the imbalance between gravity and insufficient internal pressure, making the mid-plane collapse a localized extension of the *GMC*'s gravitational history (Matzkevich et al. 2024; Speedie et al. 2024). Here, we derive the mid-plane collapse velocity by considering quasi-static contraction prior to runaway collapse, *i.e.*:

$$\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} = -g_z. \quad (11)$$

Figure 3: Standard models for the vertical density profile of an isothermal disk, in units of the disk scale height H . The solid red line shows the gaussian density profile valid for $z \ll R$, the dashed red line shows the exact solution relaxing this assumption. Because the effective gravity increases with height (and vanishes at the mid-plane) this standard disk profile is gaussian, rather than exponential as in a thin isothermal planetary atmosphere (Armitage 2017).

In the thin disk approximation (also *see.*, Schmitz 1990), where $H \ll R$, the vertical component of gravity is linear in the direction of z , i.e., $g_z = \Omega^2 z$. Assuming an isothermal disk, the pressure and density are related by $P = c_s^2 \rho$, thus leading to:

$$c_s^2 \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z} = -\Omega^2 z. \quad (12)$$

This therefore simplifies to:

$$\frac{\partial \ln \rho}{\partial z} = -\frac{\Omega^2 z}{c_s^2}. \quad (13)$$

Performing integration on both the left and right hand side of Eq. (13) yields the vertical density profile:

$$\frac{\rho(z)}{\rho_0} = \exp\left(-\frac{z^2}{2H^2}\right). \quad (14)$$

Such an equilibrium assumes that the pressure gradient is sufficient to counteract the effects of gravitational collapse. However, if the perturbation leads to a significant reduction in the internal pressure, then gravitational collapse becomes inevitable, *i.e.*:

$$\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} < g_z, \quad (15)$$

If cooling or mass loading reduces c_s or increases ρ locally, this inequality holds, and the gas parcel accelerates downwards towards the mid-plane (Armitage 2017). However, if we neglect the pressure term after the equilibrium breaks down, then the equation of motion for a fluid element becomes:

$$\frac{d^2 z}{dt^2} = -\Omega^2 z. \quad (16)$$

This is the equation of a harmonic oscillator, but in the limit where the restoring pressure is no longer sufficient and z is finite, the material behaves as if it were at free-fall towards the mid-plane of the disk (see., Lou & Shen 2004). Thus, Eq. (16) is an equation for a simple harmonic motion, but here it describes the vertical collapse of a pressureless fluid element in a disk under gravity. Larson 1969 and Penston 1969 independently came-up with the self-similar solution for Eq. (16), for a finite-time collapse solution for a self-gravitating cloud of gas and dust, *i.e.*:

$$z(t) \sim z_0 \left(1 - \frac{t}{t_{\text{ff}}}\right)^{2/3}, \quad (17)$$

where z_0 represents the initial vertical height of the fluid element at $t = 0$. For such motion, the self-similar solution approximates to a free-fall velocity:

$$V_{\text{ff},z} = -\frac{2H}{3t_{\text{ff}}}. \quad (18)$$

The result in (18) is a similarity solution of (17) and its complete derivation is presented in Appendix A of this reading. Expressing Eq. (18) and Eq. (10) as a linear combination yields:

$$\vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{orb}} = -\frac{2R}{3t_{\text{ff}}} \hat{\mathbf{r}} - \frac{2H}{3t_{\text{ff}}} \hat{\mathbf{z}} \quad (19)$$

Thus, according to (18), the vertical component of the free-fall velocity must vanish at the disk's mid-plane (*i.e.*, $H = 0$), leaving only the radial component to contribute to the homologous motion of the particle in the disk (also *see.*, Figure 4).

4.2.1 The Condition for Orbital Stability

Following the derivation of the mid-plane analogue of the free-fall velocity, attention must now be focused towards validating it against rotational constraints. The self-similar solution of Larson 1969 and Penston 1969 presented in the preceding analysis, revealed that — gravitational in-fall towards the disk's mid-plane proceeds unimpeded in the absence of pressure support at a velocity $\vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{orb}} = -2\vec{\mathbf{R}}/3t_{\text{ff}}$. This brings us to the notion that, any viable model of the protoplanetary disk's evolution must also account for the orbital dynamics inherited from the progenitor molecular cloud. This means that, in a young protoplanetary disk, gravitational contraction does not occur in isolation; it is fundamentally constrained by the requirement that the orbital motion of the disk remain consistent with the evolving gravitational field. In-order to preserve the angular momentum signature inherited from the collapse of the progenitor cloud, the orbital velocity must be precisely balanced with the free-fall velocity of the rotating molecular cloud *i.e.*:

$$\frac{\vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{orb}}}{\vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{ff}}} = 1. \quad (20)$$

If a condition contrary to this was to establish within the disk (*i.e.*, $\vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{orb}}/\vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{ff}} < 1$), then the resulting angular momentum loss surely must lead to a rapid increase in the mass accretion rate $\dot{M} = \frac{3\pi\nu\Sigma}{1-\sqrt{R_{\text{in}}/R}}$ of the YSO; where Σ is the surface density (*see.*, Shakura & Sunyaev 1973). Conversely, if the orbital velocity exceeds the free-fall velocity (*i.e.*, $\vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{orb}}/\vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{ff}} > 1$),

then the centrifugal force becomes more dominant over gravitational collapse. The resulting outward migration leads to a loss in the orbital trajectory, eventually causing the disk material to disperse. This leaves the condition presented in (20) as the only one which is compatible with the idea of orbital stability.

Figure 4: A cartoon of a *YSO* surrounded by a nascent protoplanetary disk is shown. Rather than being strictly planar, particles orbiting within the disk are tilted, giving them a three-dimensional trajectory above the mid-plane of the disk. Due to the irradiance instability, the perturbation in the disk annulus leads to an inclined inflection $\Delta H \propto H_{\text{rad}}$. The radial component $V_{\text{orb},r} = R\Omega \cos\theta$ is rotating in the azimuthal direction.

4.3 The Inclined Orbit Scenario

The orbital velocity of a particle is expressed in vector form as $\vec{V}_{\text{orb}} = \vec{R} \times \vec{\Omega}$. To determine the orbital velocity vector of the particle when it is now orbiting at an inclination θ relative to the mid-plane of the disk, the particle must be located at an altitude, $z = |\vec{H}|$ above the disk's mid-plane. Since the particle is now rotating at an angle θ (*see.*, Figure 4) relative to the mid-plane, the inclination introduces a vertical component $V_{\text{orb},z}$ to its orbital velocity vector. This particle is also rotating in the azimuthal direction ϕ_a around the *YSO* (*see.*, Webb et al. 2014) thus we have:

$$\vec{V}_{\text{orb}} = R\Omega \cos\theta \cos\phi_a \hat{r} + R\Omega \cos\theta \sin\phi_a \hat{\phi}_a + R\Omega \sin\theta \hat{z} \quad (21)$$

In a pressure-supported stratified disk structure, the azimuthal angle ϕ_a is effectively zero, as the radiative field is simulated as axisymmetric in this current model; thus, any net radiative force in the azimuthal direction averages out to zero due to this symmetry, *i.e.*:

$$\vec{V}_{\text{orb}} = R\Omega \cos\theta \hat{r} + R\Omega \sin\theta \hat{z} \quad (22)$$

The orbital inclination θ reduces the effective orbital speed to $V_{\text{orb},r} = R\Omega \cos \theta$ by disrupting the Keplerian balance while promoting radial drift. On the other hand, the vertical component $V_{\text{orb},z} = R\Omega \sin \theta$ trigger periodic excursions above or below the mid-plane as θ fluctuates. These vertical oscillations — as we will show in the following section — are attenuated by radiative cooling, which leads to eventual particle settling above the mid-plane of the disk.

5 THE RDSH MODEL

5.1 The Tracer Scale Height

In Section 2, we highlighted that, the external radiative flux from the YSO destabilizes the disk's annulus and the atmospheric layer (*see.*, Figure 4) by altering the balance of heating and cooling in a manner that amplifies both vertical and radial perturbations (Montesinos et al. 2021; Haworth et al. 2016a). Here, we show that — once star light penetrates the deeper layers of the disk, the slope of the SSOS contour line increases by $\Delta H_{\text{rad}}/\Delta R$. This perturbation allows more star light to penetrate, leading to an increase in dust heating and a corresponding rise in the local sound speed. At this point, one can now assert that, in principle, such a disk surely must exist at a knife-edge balance between stability and gravitational collapse. For stability, the random thermal motion of the gaseous particles must generate enough pressure to counterbalance the inward gravitational pull towards the mid-plane of the disk, and *vice versa*. Having made this assumption, we now proceed to seek for the most plausible definition of the radiative scale height, by first considering the condition of orbital stability presented in Eq. (20), *i.e.*:

$$\vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{ff}} = \vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{orb}} \quad (23)$$

Thus, if we try to modify (23) by introducing a restorative component to its gravitational field vector, then we will be able to account for the influence of thermal-radiative pressure in the vertical stability of the disk *i.e.*:

$$\vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{ff}} - (\vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{therm}} + \vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{rad}}) = \vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{orb}}, \quad (24)$$

:where $\vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{therm}} = C_s \hat{\mathbf{z}}$ and $\vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{rad}} = V_{\text{rad}} \hat{\mathbf{z}}$. In Section 4, we motivated our reader to consider that — the expression $V_{\text{orb},z} = |\vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{orb}}| \sin \theta$ must hold for a particle orbiting at an angle θ relative to the mid-plane of the disk. We then expressed this vertical component as $V_{\text{orb},z} = R\Omega \times \sin \theta$. But, for small orbital inclinations, $\sin \theta \sim \epsilon$, where $\epsilon = H/R$ is the disk's aspect ratio. The disk aspect ratio ϵ characterizes the disk's vertical extent relative to its radial distance, with larger values indicating a 'puffier disk'. For example, Saturn's ring system has an relatively small disk aspect ratio of about $\epsilon = 10^{-6}$ (Charnoz et al. 2009). This means that the rings of Saturn are exceptionally thin and dynamically constrained to a nearly two-dimensional plane.

This low disk aspect ratio indicates that vertical support is not provided by thermal or radiative pressure but by the collective effects of particle collisions and self-gravity. This leads to a highly flattened, pressure-insensitive vertical structure (Brilliantov et al. 2015). Therefore, the vertical component of the orbital velocity, $V_{\text{orb},z} = R\Omega \times \sin \theta$ at a tilted angle reduces to $V_{\text{orb},z} = R\Omega \times \epsilon$. Simplifying this expression further yields $\vec{\mathbf{V}}_{\text{orb},z} = H\Omega \hat{\mathbf{z}}$. What this means is

that, for a particle on a slightly inclined orbit, its vertical component, $V_{\text{orb},z} = H\Omega$, arises from the coupling between the disk's differential rotation and the particle's vertical displacement. This implies that the vertical motion is inherently sub-Keplerian, with velocities reduced by a factor of $\epsilon \ll 1$ relative to the dominant azimuthal motion. This result also agrees with the thin-disk approximation (*see.*, Schmitz 1990). In protoplanetary disks however, this scaling elucidates the occurrence of vertical oscillations such as warps and bending waves and how they propagate at speeds suppressed by the disk's aspect ratio relative to Keplerian motion. Therefore Eq. (24), simplifies to:

$$\vec{V}_{\text{ff}} - (\vec{V}_{\text{therm}} + \vec{V}_{\text{rad}}) = \Omega H \hat{z}. \quad (25)$$

If we further rationalize Eq. (25) by dividing throughout the entire expression by the Keplerian angular velocity Ω , then we will be able to establish the conditions under which the thermal-radiative pressure is sufficient to keep the particle orbiting at a stable altitude. This yields:

$$\frac{V_{\text{ff}}}{\Omega} \hat{z} - \frac{C_s}{\Omega} \hat{z} - \frac{V_{\text{rad}}}{\Omega} \hat{z} = H \hat{z}. \quad (26)$$

From Equation (26), it is apparent that the ratios C_s/Ω and V_{rad}/Ω corresponds to the thermal and radiative scale heights respectively. For that reason, we can now express these two linear terms as *i.e.*:

$$H_{\text{therm}} = \frac{C_s}{\Omega} \quad \text{and} \quad H_{\text{rad}} = \frac{V_{\text{rad}}}{\Omega}.$$

Given these considerations, we can assert that, $H_{\text{Dyn}} = V_{\text{ff}}/\Omega$ is the baseline elevation of the particle in the absence of thermal and radiative pressure support. From a purely mechanical consideration, such a condition of dynamical equilibrium yields a zero-pressure baseline solution of the form $H_{\text{Dyn}} = 0.6R$. If we substitute the linear parameters (*i.e.*, H_{Dyn} , H_{therm} and H_{rad}) into (26), then the combination of parameters yields a characteristic scale height of the form:

$$H_{\text{tracer}} = H_{\text{Dyn}} - (H_{\text{therm}} + H_{\text{rad}}). \quad (27)$$

The physics at play in a disk constrained by H_{Dyn} will be discussed extensively in Section 6.2, where we show that the tracer scale height H_{tracer} dynamically modifies the maximum vertical extent at which the molecular species remains suspended and detectable when gravity and the thermal-radiative pressure exists at dynamical equilibrium. Next, we seek to validate the result presented in (27), by conducting a numerical investigation on the Herbig Ae/Be star HD 100546 protoplanetary disk. There, we investigate the efficacy of the RDSH model in estimating the spatial distribution of gaseous tracers (e.g., CO) above the mid-plane of the disk.

6 RESULTS AND GENERAL DISCUSSIONS

6.1 The HD 100546 Protoplanetary Disk

To get a feel of the possible value that our RDSH model shall possibly bring, we analyze the thermal and spectral distribution profile of the protoplanetary disk of HD 100546 across a radial distance of 70 AU (*see.*, Table 2 for the stellar parameters). HD 100546 is a Herbig

Ae/Be star which shows structures that suggest the presence of two companions in the disk at 10 and 64 AU Currie et al. 2015. The outer companion seems to be in the act of formation.

Table 2: Stellar parameters for HD 100546 (based on Quanz et al. 2015). Rameau et al. 2017 and Quanz et al. 2015 reported that the star is located at a distance of 110 pc and has a mass of $2.66M_{\odot}$.

T_{eff} (K)	L_{\star} ($\log_{10}(L_{\odot})$)	Age (Gyr)	M_{\star} M_{\odot}	Sp. T —	ρ_{\star} (g/cm^3)	R_{\star} (R_{\odot})	$\log g$ ($\log_{10}(\text{cm/s}^2)$)
10331	1.546957	0.0055	2.66	—	0.5895344	1.8528800	4.32726

The strong observational signature of the embedded protoplanets at 10 and 70 AU (Pinilla, P. et al. 2015), inferred from localized excess emission and gas kinematics, strongly suggests that when the two protoplanets are detected, the results can be directly compared to observed gas structures traced by molecules such as the CO Isotopologues, which is crucial in validating our present hydrodynamical model. This renders HD 100546 a more candid testbed in this present study. The radial temperature profile and the ancillary information used in modeling the scale height distribution of the gases in HD 100546, where obtained from Quanz et al. 2015 and Rameau et al. 2017.

6.2 The Dynamical Scale Height

The vertical confinement of particles in slightly inclined orbits is restricted by the dynamic scale height $H_{\text{Dyn}} = 0.6R$, which acts as a dynamical ceiling on vertical excursions above the thermal and radiative scale heights ($H_{\text{TR}} = H_{\text{therm}} + H_{\text{rad}}$). In the vicinity of the mid-plane, the gravitational potential may be approximated by a harmonic oscillator potential (Lynden-Bell & Pringle 1974) of the form $\Phi(z) = \frac{1}{2}m\Omega^2z^2$, implying that the vertical motion of a displaced particle is equivalent to that of a simple harmonic oscillator (Sarkar & Jog 2022) near the mid-plane of the disk. In this scenario, the total mechanical energy of the particle remains constant, so the initial kinetic energy it possesses due to its epicyclic motion and the thermal-radiative pressure must be converted to potential energy at the point of maximum vertical displacement, where the speed momentarily vanishes and the energy is stored entirely as $\Phi(H) = \frac{1}{2}m\Omega^2H_{\text{Dyn}}^2$. This correspondence between the initial kinetic state and the final potential configuration defines the vertical amplitude of oscillation as:

$$\frac{1}{2}m\Omega^2H_{\text{Dyn}}^2 = \frac{1}{2}mV_{\text{ff}}^2. \quad (28)$$

Table 3: Disk aspect ratio (H_{Dyn}/R) profile for HD 100546 over the radial range $1 < R < 70$ AU, assuming a dynamical scale height of $H_{\text{Dyn}} = 0.6R$.

Radial Distance (AU)	Ω S^{-1}	H_{Dyn} (AU)	H_{Dyn}/R
1	3.08e-7	0.60	0.600
5	2.76e-8	2.83	0.566
17	4.40e-9	10.20	0.600
34	1.56e-9	20.40	0.600
45	1.02e-9	27.00	0.600
70	5.26e-10	42.00	0.600

Notice how the expression in (28) recovers the expected dynamic scale height $H_{\text{Dyn}} = V_{\text{ff}}/\Omega$. At this critical distance, gravity exists at equilibrium with the outward centrifugal force. This solution also recovers the classical energy conservation law of a harmonic oscillator, but with the system dynamics uniquely characterized by the collapse velocity, V_{ff} . As the particle free-falls towards the mid-plane of the disk, the gravitational potential energy is converted back to kinetic energy (also *see.*, Schmitz 1990 and Sarkar & Jog 2022). This downward acceleration is opposed by the thermal-radiative pressure gradient, which decelerates the particle until the vertical velocity reaches zero at $H_{\text{TR}} = H_{\text{therm}} + H_{\text{rad}}$, where the kinetic energy is converted back to gravitational potential energy. This particle loses its potential energy and reverses direction towards H_{Dyn} and begins ascending while repeating the initial cycle.

Figure 5: Plot of the disk aspect ratio and dynamic scale height plotted against a common radial distance R for the protoplanetary disk around HD 100546.

The data, detailed in Table 3 and visualized in Figure 5, presents the dynamic scale height for H_{Dyn} , computed under the assumption that vertical support arises solely from the equilibrium between gravity and the centrifugal force. Over much of the disk, H_{Dyn} scales linearly with the radial distance, leading to an approximately constant disk aspect ratio. The invariance of this ratio indicates a flared disk structure, which allows irradiation to penetrate through the outer layers more efficiently. However, a significant deviation occurs near $R = 0.3 \text{ AU}$, where the disk aspect ratio dips to $H/R \sim 0.566$ before returning to its nominal value. This localized depression in the disk scale height likely corresponds to the disk sublimation zone.

This deviation can be attributed to the high luminosity and strong UV output of the Herbig Be star (Tatulli et al. 2011; Grady et al. 2005) HD 100546, which could lead to enhanced photodestruction of dust grains, pushing the sublimation front outwards. In this region, sublimated dust is rapidly swept away, forming a partially evacuated cavity and a transitional wall of high opacity at the boundary of the sublimation front. In the case of HD 100546, its disk sublimation region is approximately $R = 0.24 \text{ AU}$ (see., Grady et al. 2005), which gives us a 25% deviation from the inferred value. This opacity wall acts as a radiative barrier that casts a shadow over parts of the disk further out, temporarily suppressing the vertical temperature gradient and diminishing the effects of irradiation-driven instabilities. Due to the high opacity dust sublimation front, fewer photons penetrate into the deeper layers, leading to a transient decrease in thermal support and a corresponding reduction in the local scale height. Once past this sublimation front, the disk regains its flaring geometry, and the aspect ratio stabilizes as the opacity returns to more typical values, restoring the vertical expansion supported by the thermal-radiative pressure.

6.3 The Radiative Scale Height

Thus far, we have identified the upper limit for vertical excursions (H_{Dyn}) in a pressure supported disk. We have also made the assumption that, once star light penetrates the deeper layers of the disk, the slope of the SSOS contour line increases by $m_{\text{rad}} = \Delta H_{\text{rad}}/\Delta R$. To validate this hypothesis, we consider a simplified scenario of a young protostellar system which, at some point along its evolution, begins to emit high-energy photons (*e.g.*, X-rays and UV radiation), thereby triggering the irradiative instability. Due to the photon driven instability, the SSOS contour line deviates by a gradient m_{rad} (see., Figure 6). We note that, the steepness of the gradient m_{rad} , depends of the radiative scale height.

Following this shear offset, more star light penetrates deeper into the disk, thus increasing the local temperature and sound speed. This leads to an unprecedented increase in the thermal pressure. This means that the gaseous species is confined to the layer bounded by H_{TR} and H_{Dyn} (see., Figure 7). In such a scenario, gravity attracts particles towards the mid-plane, while the thermal-radiative pressure provides an upward pressure support. If the particles remain confined between the two layers, then the resulting equilibrium manifests in the form of mechanical undulations, with observable signatures that can serve as kinematic tracers of the disk structure. With this theoretical framework in place, we now proceed to test our RDSH hypothesis on the disk surrounding HD 100546.

Table 4: Scale height models for dominant gaseous species (H, He, e^-, CO) in the protoplanetary disk of HD 100546.

R	T	H_{therm}	H_{Dyn}	H_{rad}	H_{rad}	H_{rad}	H_{rad}
(AU)	(K)	(AU)	(AU)	Hydrogen ($\times 10^7 m$)	Electrons ($\times 10^9 m$)	Helium ($\times 10^6 m$)	CO ($\times 10^5 m$)
1	1500	4.73e 2	6.00e 1	6.31e 2	1.16e+0	1.59e 1	2.27e 1
5	700	3.61e 1	2.83e+0	3.30e 1	6.05e+0	8.28e 1	1.18e+0
17	500	1.91e+0	10.20e+0	1.47e+0	2.71e+1	3.71e+0	5.30e+0
34	220	3.60e+0	20.40e+0	1.84e+0	3.37e+1	4.61e+0	6.60e+0
45	100	3.69e+0	27.00e+0	1.27e+0	2.33e+1	3.18e+0	4.56e+0
70	70	6.00e+0	42.00e+0	1.72e+1	3.16e+2	4.24e+0	6.20e+0

Figure 6: Logarithmic scale heights (Log H) of radiative, thermal, and dynamic origin are plotted on a common radial axis for selected primordial gaseous species—CO, H, He, and free electrons—in the protoplanetary disk surrounding the young stellar object HD 100546.

Figure 6 shows the radiative scale heights of key primordial gaseous species in HD 100546's protoplanetary disk, for a system initially in a compact, thermally relaxed configuration. Each gaseous component is characterized by a distinct contour line which corresponds to a unique SSOS. The SSOS_n traces the observable photospheric layer of the gaseous species and is char-

acterized by an optical depth of $\tau = 1$. The elevation of each SSOS line introduces a unique angle ϕ relative to the photon’s original trajectory. For example, the gradient m_{rad} for molecular hydrogen is characterized by a lower and upper SSOS limit of $SSOS_{H_2}$ and $SSOS_e$ respectively. The radiative transfer velocity has a vertical component $v_{\text{rad}} \sin \phi$, which acts upwards, in a direction opposite the hydrostatic pressure gradient generated by P_{TR} . This motion is most efficient when the KE is maximum when $\phi = 90^\circ$ and zero at $SSOS_{H_2}$. When molecular hydrogen achieves maximum kinetic energy, the gradient m_{rad} becomes more pronounced and more photons penetrate the disk, thus leading to runaway radiative heating. The particles are lifted vertically upwards by the buildup in thermal-radiative pressure, reaching a maximum scale height $H_{\text{TR}} < H_{\text{tracer}} < H_{\text{Dyn}}$. The magnitude of H_{tracer} , as shall be seen next, depends on the particle mass and the wavelength of the incident radiation.

6.4 The Tracer Scale Height

So far, we have hitherto demonstrated that, irradiance instability provides a compelling mechanism through which radiative feedback alters the vertical structure of the protoplanetary disk. We have also seen that, in environments surrounding young stellar objects, photons interact with gaseous particles in a manner which is proportional to the particle mass and the wavelength of the incident radiation. Here, we examine the consistency of our H_{tracer} model with the vertical CO distribution observed by ALMA in the protoplanetary disks of HD 100546, PDS 70, and HD 163296, as reported by Law et al. (2022), Law et al. (2024), and Law et al. (2021), respectively.

Table 5: Scale height model of ^{12}CO near the photosphere (optical line) in the HD 100546 protoplanetary disk.

R	H_{therm}	H_{Dyn}	H_{rad}	H_{tracer}	H_{tracer}/R
(AU)	(AU)	(AU)	^{12}CO (AU)	^{12}CO AU	Disk Aspect Ratio
1	0.05	0.6	1.52e-7	0.55	0.550
5	0.36	2.83	7.89e-7	2.47	0.494
17	1.91	10.20	3.54e-6	8.29	0.488
34	3.60	20.40	4.41e-6	16.80	0.494
45	3.69	27.00	3.05e-6	23.31	0.518
70	6.00	42.00	4.14e-6	36.00	0.514

6.4.1 Observational Expectations

The vertical distribution of CO, mapped via submillimeter line emission, serves as a diagnostics for UV-driven chemistry and hydrodynamic processes in disk atmospheres, with implications for planet-forming environments (Lin et al. 2023). CO serves as an excellent tracer for primordial gas in protoplanetary disks due to its strong rotational emission lines at millimeter wavelengths. This can be attributed to its permanent dipole moment, which has enabled high-contrast detection compared to other homonuclear gaseous species like H_2 . Observations (*e.g.*, Podio, L. et al. 2020; Villenave, M. et al. 2020) shows that CO is mostly abundant at

Figure 7: The plot displays the logarithm of the thermal, radiative, dynamic, and tracer scale heights as functions of radial distance for the ^{12}CO tracer in the protoplanetary disk of the young stellar object HD 100546.

elevations where starlight can penetrate, typically at disk aspect ratios of about $0.1 < H/R < 0.5$ (Law et al. 2021, 2024) in HD 100546 and PDS 70.

CO is a tracer in the intermediate layers of protoplanetary disks due to two competing thermodynamic constraints: 1) in the cold mid-plane ($T \approx 17 - 25\text{K}$), CO undergoes freeze-out onto dust grains; and 2) in the photodissociation-dominated surface layers, stellar UV radiation destroys the molecule (Dutrey, Anne 2022). This produces a characteristic vertical distribution, where CO is optimally abundant at intermediate scale heights where temperatures permit gaseous-phase survival while the high optical depth provides sufficient shielding from the photodissociating radiation (Villenave, M. et al. 2020; Lin et al. 2023; Podio, L. et al. 2020). In Table 5, we present the results for H_{tracer} , inferred from our numerical simulation of the CO tracer in the protoplanetary disk surrounding HD 100546. The corresponding modeled CO emission layer is illustrated in Figure 7.

The disk aspect ratio for ^{12}CO decreases from $0.55 > H/R > 0.494$ between 5 AU and 45 AU leading to a reduction in the gradient of the $SSOS_{4.36}$ line within this radial range (*i.e.*, $m_{\text{rad}} = \frac{\Delta \text{Log } H}{\Delta R} \sim 0$). At such a low gradient, the disk is shielded from direct stellar radiation, leading to a disproportionate decrease in the disk aspect ratio to $H/R \sim 0.056$. These findings are widely consistent with the results returned by the ALMA MAPS survey of HD 163296, where H/R ranged between 0.3 and 0.5 at radial distances of 30–300 AU (Law et al. 2021), and for PDS 70, where $H/R = 0.3$ was observed between 15–150 AU (Law et al. 2023). A similar behavior was reported by (Stapper, L. M. et al. 2023) in the ALMA survey of HD

100546, where ^{12}CO emission revealed variations in height due to the disk structure and stellar irradiation, with H/R varying between 0.1–0.5 within a radial distance of $50 < R < 200$ AU.

7 CONCLUSION

While there are many studies into the effects of radiative pressure in the evolution of young stellar systems (see *e.g.*, Krumholz et al. 2005; Nyambuya 2010; Montesinos et al. 2021), there are curiously few studies which discuss the effects of radiative pressure on the vertical geometry of a protoplanetary disk. A key thesis of this study is that, the radiative scale height is explicitly dependent on the mass of the particle under consideration, while the thermal pressure scale height is conventionally standardized solely on the mass of hydrogen gas. Using a model based on Wu & Lithwick 2021, we have shown that this classical picture is incomplete. Our bound is the best possible bound because our PMT framework is capable of capturing the disk’s diverse composition, thus leading to a more precise and dynamic representation of the vertical and chemical structure of the disk. Moreover, in the equilibrium state between gravity and the thermal-radiative force, we have shown that particles maintain a stable altitude above the mid-plane, with the orbital disk scale height H_{Dyn} , acting as a dynamical ceiling for the vertical excursions. This configuration aligns with predictions of non-axisymmetric perturbations in the protoplanetary disk dynamics, where vertical excursions are modulated by the conserved angular momentum and energy gradients (also *see.*, Lynden-Bell & Pringle (1974) and Sarkar & Jog 2022).

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Appendix A: SIMILARITY SOLUTION FOR THE COLLAPSE VELOCITY

Here, we present a self-similar solution (also *see.*, Shu 1977; Blottiau et al. 1988) for the harmonic oscillator equation presented in Eq. (16). The collapse of the molecular cloud must proceed under the conditions where the vertical hydrostatic equilibrium has broken down, i.e., in the absence of pressure support. In this regime, the pressure gradients are no longer sufficient to balance the gravitational collapse, and the motion of the gas and dust is dominated by the disk's mid-plane (Lou & Shen 2004). The vertical displacement $z(t)$ of a fluid element undergoing collapse can be approximated by a similarity solution to the pressureless gravitational collapse equation in Eq. (17), as *i.e.*:

$$z(t) \sim z_0 \left(1 - \frac{t}{t_{\text{ff}}}\right)^{2/3}. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

When the pressure gradient no longer provide support, the vertical motion reduces to that of a particle at free-fall under a constant or slowly varying gravitational field. The particle's trajectory begins to follow a nonlinear evolutionary track as it collapses towards the disk's mid-plane. To establish $V_{\text{orb},z}$, we differentiate (A.1) with respect to time. Thus we have:

$$V_{\text{orb},z} = \frac{dz}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \left[z_0 \left(1 - \frac{t}{t_{\text{ff}}}\right)^{2/3} \right]. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

This simplifies to:

$$V_{\text{orb},z} = -\frac{2z_0}{3t_{\text{ff}}} \left(1 - \frac{t}{t_{\text{ff}}}\right)^{-1/3}. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Recognizing that $z(t)$ itself evolves as $\sim (1 - t/t_{\text{ff}})^{2/3}$, we can invert the similarity relation to express the velocity directly in terms of the instantaneous displacement and time. Thus, taking up a proportion for t and z from Eq. (A.1) yields:

$$z(t) = z_0 \left(1 - \frac{t}{t_{\text{ff}}}\right)^{2/3} \implies \left(\frac{z(t)}{z_0}\right)^{3/2} = \left(1 - \frac{t}{t_{\text{ff}}}\right) \implies \left(\frac{z(t)}{z_0}\right)^{3/2} = (1 - tt_{\text{ff}}^{-1}). \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Substitute the time-dependent component of the similarity solution into Eq. (A.3) gives:

$$V_{\text{orb},z} = -\frac{2z_0}{3t_{\text{ff}}} \left(\left(\frac{z(t)}{z_0}\right)^{3/2}\right)^{-1/3} \implies = -\frac{2z_0}{3t_{\text{ff}}} \left(\frac{z(t)}{z_0}\right)^{-1/2} \implies = -\frac{2}{3t_{\text{ff}}} \cdot \frac{z_0^{3/2}}{\sqrt{z(t)}}. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Eq. (A.5) results in an increase in magnitude of the in-fall velocity as collapse continues and the velocity diverges at a terminal $t \rightarrow t_{\text{ff}}$. This divergence represents a rapid acceleration phase of the fluid element as it approaches the mid-plane of the disk, thus the condition $z_0 \equiv z(t_0)$ must hold for the initial collapse phase of the pressureless fluid element, *i.e.*:

$$V_{\text{orb},z} = -\frac{2H}{3t}. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Eq. (A.6) therefore offers a mathematically grounded velocity vector field of mid-plane collapse, in the absence of pressure support.

Appendix B: IMAGE OF THE PROTOPLANETARY DISC IRAS 04302+2247 OBSERVED EDGE-ON BY ALMA AT SUB- MILLIMETER WAVELENGTHS

The high-resolution images presented in Figure B.1, reveals a striking, flattened structure with prominent dark lanes bisecting the disk, likely caused by dust settling and grain growth in the mid-plane. The ALMA observations reveals the disk's vertical stratification and possible insights into the dynamics of dust and gas in the absence of strong turbulence (Villenave, M. et al. 2020). Asymmetries in the disk's emission suggest possible perturbations from embedded protoplanets or gravitational instabilities. The vertical brightness asymmetry (*e.g.*, one side appearing brighter) might reflect temperature differences or non-uniform irradiation from the central star, thus offering clues about the thermal structure of the disk (Podio, L. et al. 2020).

Figure B.1: The protoplanetary disc IRAS 04302+2247 observed edge-on with ALMA at sub-millimeter wavelengths (0.9–1.3 mm). The continuum emission (top left panel) comes from the dust grains sedimented in the disk plane (in orange) where the planets will form. The line emission of ^{12}CO , CS and H_2CO molecules comes mainly from the molecular layer (in green), while the disc plane appears darker because many molecules freeze on the dust grains. Schematic based on: Podio, L. et al. 2020.